

NORMAL RANGE OF PROSTATIC SPECIFIC ANTIGEN AND AGE-RELATED PROSTATIC SPECIFIC ANTIGEN IN SCREENING FOR PROSTATE ADENOCARCINOMA

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Annotation

Prostate-specific antigen (PSA) has emerged as the most useful serum tumor marker in the diagnosis and screening of prostate adenocarcinoma. The current reference normal range (0 to 4.0 ng /mL monoclonal) has neither the sensitivity nor specificity to be generally accepted as a screening test, and alternatives to serum PSA have been proposed, such as PSA density, PSA velocity, and PSA adjusted for age. The age-adjusted definition of PSA takes into account the fact that the prostate enlarges as men age, and that screening should have maximum sensitivity in younger men and maximum specificity in older men.

Key words: PSA, TRUS, biopsy, prostate cancer, gland, adenocarcinoma.

There has been a marked increase in the number of reported cases of prostate adenocarcinoma worldwide over the past 10 years, with approximately 200,000 cases and 38,000 deaths expected. Adenocarcinoma of the prostate is not usually seen to be as aggressive as some cancers such as lung cancer; a North American man was diagnosed with prostate cancer in his mid-60s. You are more likely to die from cancer than from any other cause. There are 2 large controlled studies that have demonstrated a clear benefit of screening for prostate adenocarcinoma, although increased public awareness has contributed to screening activity.

Now considered to provide the most sensitive method for detecting early cancer. However, PSA suffers from both a lack of sensitivity (about 79%) and specificity (about 59%), limiting its usefulness.6-c. Attempts to improve sensitivity and specificity include normalizing PSA level to gland volume, PSA density (PSAD), PSA transition zone volume (PSAT),12 PSA change over time (PSA velocity), r3 , t4 , and adjusting PSA for age. PSA age ranges take into account that prostatic hyperplasia increases PSA as the patient ages, and that groups that may benefit most from screening (younger patients) should have a normal range providing maximum sensitivity, whereas those that will benefit less (elderly patients) require maximum specificity t 5 The adoption of age-specific PSA ranges does not end the significant overlap between benign and malignant groups due to the fact that prostatic hyperplasia is not a universal phenomenon . expressed with age. We examined our data to determine sensitivity, specificity, and positive predictive values for the normal PSA range (0 to 4 ng /mL) compared with age-specific PSA values.

MATERIAL AND METHODS. Men aged 40 to 79 years were referred for transrectal surgery. Ultrasound of the prostate due to an elevated PSA (more than 4.0 ng /ml), an abnormal DRE value, or both an elevated PSA and an abnormal DRE.

TRANSRECTAL ULTRASONOGRAPHY

Transrectal ultrasound of the prostate (TRUS) was performed for all patients, with some patients undergoing multiple examinations over time. Biopsy criteria included an elevated PSA

level. (more than 4 ng /ml), PSA density more than 0.15, abnormal DRE or suspicious areas on TRUS. All ultrasound examinations were performed using the standard method described previously.

PATIENT STRATIFICATION

Patients were stratified by age (decade) and DRE result. Previously proposed age ranges were used (0 to 2.5 ng /ml for children 40 to 49 years old, 0 to 3.5 ng /ml for children aged 50 to 59 years, 0 to 4.5 ng /ml at ages 60 to 69 years and 0 to 6.5 ng /ml at ages 70 to 79 years).15 PSA determination was either the monoclonal method (Hybritech: normal, 0 to 4 ng /ml) or the monoclonal/polyclonal method 1 (Abbott IMX: normal, from 0 to 3.8 ng /ml).

Sensitivity was calculated using the number of positive biopsies as the denominator, and specificity was calculated using the number of negative biopsies and patients with normal ultrasound examinations as the denominator. A total of 4,710 patients were examined, with multiple examinations in some patients. The total number of ultrasound examinations was 5629.

RESULTS

Patients were stratified by age by decade and DRE (Table I). There were 299 1 abnormal prostates detected on TRUS, a total of 2657 prostate biopsies were performed, of which 945 were positive for adenocarcinoma (35.6%). A total of 2462 patients had abnormal findings. (more than 4.0 ng /ml) PSA, of which 1449 were negative. Tables II and III show the sensitivity, specificity, and positive predictive value for these patients. In this group, 3025 ultrasounds and 183 biopsies were performed. The overall positive biopsy result was 43.5%. In the DRE-negative subgroup, 1830 ultrasounds and 866 biopsies were performed. completed, of which 235 (27%) were positive. When stratified by age group (ultrasound), the biopsy positivity rate was 5.5%, 19.5%, 23.4%, and 29.9% for groups 1, 2, 3, and 4, respectively. In those patients who had a normal DRE, the rates of positive biopsies (ultrasound) years) were 7.7%, 10.8%, 11.9% and 15.5% for age groups.

Of the 2094 patients, 1195 had elevated PSA compared to the age range. IF negative. In this group, there were 2574 ultrasound scans and 165 1 biopsies were performed. There were 740 positive biopsies, for an overall positive biopsy rate of 44.8%. In the subgroup of DRE-negative patients, 1526 ultrasound scans were performed with 780 biopsies, of which 218 (28%) were positive.

When stratified by age group, the incidence of positive biopsies (ultrasound studies) was 14.8%, 18.8%, 24.6% and 36.4% for groups 1, 2, 3 and 4, respectively. When we consider only those patients whose DRE was negative, the rates of positive biopsy (ultrasound) were 10.5%, 10.6%, 12.6%, and 20.6% for groups 1, 2, 3, and 4, respectively. .

Due to the small number of patients in group 1 (age 40 to 49 years) with a positive biopsy (n = 5) no meaningful statistical information could be generated. In the 2nd age group there was a slight increase. sensitivity when age range was used; and in group 3 there was a slight increase in specificity with age ranges. In age group 4, age-specific PSA was 21% more specific than normal-range PSA (at the expense of a 13% reduction in sensitivity), for an overall increase in positive prediction cost of 8%. If the groups were stratified. DRE results showed a slight advantage in the positive predictive value of age-specific PSA levels above standard ranges in predicting biopsy outcome. In patients aged 70 to 79 years with negative DREs, the use of age-

specific PSA increased specificity by 14% at the expense of decreased sensitivity by 13%, but increased positive predictive value by 19% to 26%.

The PSA level was 3.5 ng /ml (sensitivity 94%, 65% specificity), and for group 3 the optimal level was 5.0 ng /ml (sensitivity 79%, specificity 62%). In group 4, due to the progressive rise in the curve, the ideal PSA was more difficult to determine, but PSA 7 ng /ml sensitivity was 75% and specificity was 70%.

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